

DULA2X UG SAYAW2X RA NI: THE EXPERIENCES OF COLLEGE PE STUDENTS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION CURRICULUM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 2

Pages: 130-134

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2247

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13362291

Manuscript Accepted: 06-10-2024

DULA2x ug SAYAW2x RA NI: The Experiences of College PE Students in the Implementation of Physical Education Curriculum

Eliseo V. Villaganas Jr.*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to describe the experiences of College PE students in implementing the Physical Education Curriculum, coping mechanisms for the challenges encountered, and the learning insights observed. Five participants in the study were second-year college students from Notre Dame of Marbel University, taking PE122 Team Sports subject. The status of the implementation of physical education was geared toward two significant themes: satisfying the students in the teaching instruction and enjoying the Physical Activities. At the same time, the coping mechanism for the challenges in implementing physical education was geared toward two significant themes: worry and lacking a positive attitude towards learning the skills and boosting confidence in performing the skills. In addition, the learning insights drawn to improve the implementation of physical education at the tertiary level are presented in two major themes: improving the learning instructions and providing holistic development activities to students. The Commission on Higher Education should consider the needs of the learners and teachers in planning the Physical Education subject to implement the Physical Education curriculum at the tertiary level effectively. The teacher applies unique teaching styles to activate the participation of the students in the physical activities and provide meaningful learning experiences to students.

Keywords: *experiences, college pe students, physical education curriculum*

Introduction

Physical education is part of the curriculum that can be taken in college in any course. This subject requires skills development through different physical activities given by the teacher. However, some of the students have been underrated in this subject. The curriculum implementation is one basis for determining the students' behavior toward learning Physical education subjects. Moreover, the teacher plays a significant role in providing meaningful learning experiences for the students that would change the understatement of the subject PE Lang. This phenomenological study would help develop a teaching framework that effectively implements the Tertiary PE Curriculum for students.

In Slovenia, quality PE depends on five factors: allocated time, available facilities and equipment, the contents of the PE curriculum, the number of children per teacher, and teacher competencies. The PE curriculum and its quality implementation determine the PE outcomes among these factors. The implementation of the curriculum, in disparity, depends on teachers' teaching competencies. (Starc & Strel, 2012) Hence, these factors have been significant in developing a teaching framework for Physical Education subjects. Also, the students' experiences in implementing the curriculum could help improve the pedagogy in teaching PE subjects.

The delivery of instruction in tertiary Physical Education during the transition years of K to 12 was due to the implementation of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 in the Philippines. The conclusions were drawn that duplicating activities in senior high school Physical Education and Physical Fitness and Self-Testing Activities caused boredom, which later led to their loss of interest in the subject. Also, the practice of giving equivalent grades to the student's scores on the Physical Fitness Test and giving too many take-home tasks in Physical Education classes cause additional stress and pressure on the students because they feel threatened that failing to get higher scores on the Physical Fitness Test or failing to comply with all the tasks will result to a low grade in Physical Education. Furthermore, teachers' high expectations cause students to push themselves beyond their limits, bringing more anxiety. On the other hand, teachers' absenteeism demotivates students to learn in Physical Education. This causes additional stress, too, as lessons are rushed by their teachers every time, and they fail to meet in one session. With this, their learning was compromised, for they will do their Physical Education tasks for compliance. (Tagare & Villaluz, 2021)

Generation Z students were the study participants at the University of Southern Mindanao, Kabacan, who were tasked to enhance the Tertiary Physical Education curriculum content. The researchers used focus group discussions, interviews, and extensive observations that resulted in five concerns: fewer lectures, practical activities needing minimal competition programs, and group activities. According to Tagare (2021), the participation of students in recreational activities was a good predictor of academic grades, even when achievement test scores were considered in a sample of middle school and college students. Learning is more enjoyable and meaningful for them if they can participate in various activities that help them grow their whole selves. Also, it will boost their confidence and involvement, resulting in increased participation in Physical Education classes. In addition, the research participants indicated they were dissatisfied with physical education due to excessive lectures. Generation Z Students minimized the intensely competitive learning activities in their Physical Education classes to alleviate the strain. They emphasized that making competitive group assignments is unjust because they do not share the same competencies; thus, some will receive a high grade due to their talent, while others will not because it is not their field. Hence, they prefer group collaborations over individual tasks because they foster a more harmonious

relationship with their peers and boost their morale while completing an academic mission. Moreover, it is much more beneficial to include community activities in Tertiary Physical Education to alleviate their shyness and produce high-quality outputs through their collective efforts.

As an experienced teacher teaching Public School, Senior High School, and tertiary level, Physical Education subjects have been urged to conduct this study to determine the effective implementation of the Physical Education curriculum at different levels. The students' experiences implementing Tertiary Physical Education have been studied to improve the curriculum and provide meaningful learning experiences. Teaching frameworks were developed to address the needs of the students. However, there is a need to conduct a study in different regions to determine the needs of the students and teachers to effectively implement the Tertiary Physical Education Curriculum in other Colleges and Universities. This study will help develop a localized Tertiary Physical Education curriculum teaching framework. The researcher would be able to determine the challenges and difficulties of the students in coping with the subject. The publication of this study locally, regionally, and nationally would help to improve the Tertiary Physical Education curriculum. Moreover, this study will be the basis for other researchers to improve the delivery of PE and provide active participation of college students in different colleges and universities.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of PE College students in implementing the Physical Education Curriculum?
2. What are the challenges in learning the subject of Physical Education?
3. What learning insights can be drawn from their experiences to improve the implementation of the Physical Education curriculum?

Methodology

This study utilized a qualitative research method, employing a phenomenological approach. This involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences. It was used to gather in-depth insights into a problem or generate new ideas for research. The participants of this investigation were the PE 122 Team Sports students of Notre Dame of Marbel University. To ascertain the data from the study participants, the participants were PE 122 students of the said school qualified in the study. It consists of 5 students purposely selected by the researcher who will participate in the in-depth interview (IDI) and who will join the (FGD). The discussion members were picked since they coordinated involvement in the school's events. They served as the solid wellspring of information for this investigation.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the first research question of the study. It focuses on the Experiences of the PE College students regarding the implementation of the Physical Education Curriculum. For this study, I asked the participants about their experiences. Figure 1 shows the result of my thematic analysis, which summarizes the answer to the first objective of this study.

Figure 1. Experiences of the PE College students towards the Implementation of the Physical Education Curriculum

Satisfied the students in the teaching instruction. Teaching behaviors that satisfy students' need for competence fall within the need-supportive structure category. Therefore, teachers provide structure, for instance, by clearly explaining tasks and expectations to students and effectively demonstrating skills (Haerens et al., 2013). This means that teachers should provide clear instruction and demonstrate the skills to the students to satisfy their learning of the subject. Participants were satisfied with the learning experiences in implementing the PE Curriculum. As expressed by the Participant 3:

“Very specific when it comes to the instructions, and they are very enthusiastic when they conduct a specific physical activity.” P3, L3

Enjoyed the Physical Activities. According to Rheingold (2010), students who are offered a choice of physical activities are more likely to participate in class and not feel uncomfortable about being able to perform among their peers. This means that the teacher should offer varied physical activities to students so that they can participate actively in the class. Participants enjoyed the learning experiences in the implementation of the PE Curriculum. As expressed by the Participant 1:

“My experience towards the entire implementation of the PE curriculum is good because PE curriculum not only comprises of different physical activities but also incorporate health, environmental, and social aspects that would lead to holistic development of the students.” P1

This section discusses the second research question of the study, which focuses on the Challenges of Learning the Physical Education Subject. For this study, I asked the participants about their challenges in learning the subject. Figure 2 shows the result of my thematic analysis, which summarizes the answer to the second objective of this study.

Figure 2. Challenges in learning the Physical Education subject

Worried and lacked a Positive Attitude towards learning the skills. Student attitude toward physical education is moderate to high in various parts of the world and across various curricula. However, multiple factors can have an impact on attitude. Student attitude can be affected by the classroom environment (e.g., playgrounds, open spaces, recess, standardized PE curricula) and teacher behavior (Subramaniam & Silverman, 2007). This means that teachers should provide a conducive learning environment, planned activities, and instructional materials to be used in teaching. Participants were worried and lacked a positive attitude towards learning PE subjects. As expressed by the Participant 1:

“I think the factors that can affect learning physical education subject would be the time because in learning PE subject, there are topics that are broad and time is limited in discussing the lesson. And also the materials and facility, it really affects the learning of the student if we don't have these materials that we should use in learning.” P1.L2

Boost confidence in performing the skills. Self-confidence is a belief that a person has the inner sources required to succeed. In addition, the high expectation of success characterizes self-confidence. Also, it can help generate positive emotions, improve concentration, influence the setting of goals, increase commitment, and enhance the psychological strength of students. This fact concludes that a good approach to mental training is essential in sports psychology. It has been proven that self-confidence increases considerably through mental training (Plakona et al., 2014). This means that teachers should focus on skills development and develop students' mental skills to boost their confidence in performing the skills. Participants should boost confidence in performing the skills. As expressed by Participant 5:

“The factors that affect my learning Physical Education subject is that there was a time that I am lack of energy and lack of confidence because I have no skills developed in a certain sport.” P5,L2

This section provides a discussion of the third research question of the study. It focuses on the Learning insights that can be drawn from their experiences to improve the implementation of the Physical Education curriculum. For this study, I ask the participants about the learning insights that can be drawn from their experiences to improve the implementation of the Physical Education curriculum. Figure 3 shows the result of my thematic analysis, which summarizes the answer to the third objective of this study.

Figure 3. Learning insights can be drawn from their experiences to improve the implementation of the Physical Education curriculum

Improved the learning instructions. Cariaga (2014) recommended that Physical Education teachers try other teaching styles to enhance and improve the teaching of the discipline. According to Lund and Veal (2018), the teacher’s responsibility is to ensure that the students learn. This means that teachers should use varied teaching strategies to cater to the needs in any situation. The participants suggested improving the learning instructions of the teachers. As expressed by the Participant 1:

“The aspect that would improve the implementation of Physical Education Subject would be employing online/field games in teaching and learning because it gives motivation and encouragement to the students to participate in the learning/performance discussion.” P1,L3

Provided Holistic Development Activities to students. According to Ganaden (2019), quality physical education programs allow young people to develop the values, knowledge, and abilities they need to live physically active lifestyles, enhance self-esteem, and promote and enable physical exercise in others. This means teachers should provide a holistic approach to activities for students to implement the PE curriculum effectively. The participant learned that the Physical Education curriculum provides holistic development to students. As expressed by the Participant 3:

“It is really important to effectively and sufficiently implement Physical education because it is part of the holistic development of a students and lesson/topic is beneficial for the life skills of the students which they can integrate into the real world scenario.” P3.L5

Conclusions

Based on the implications of the study, I, the researcher, felt that the following are the best possible future directions: The Commission on Higher Education, as part of the Curriculum development, should consider the needs of the learners and teachers in planning the Physical Education subject that allows the students to activate and boost their self-confidence in performing the different activities. Moreover, the agency should provide PE teachers with training to improve the learning instructions in the classroom.

The school administrators, as the head of the University, provide learning materials and a learning environment to cater to the needs of the students and PE teachers, such as sports equipment, a dance room, and a conducive learning environment for students to perform the different activities. This will effectively implement the PE curriculum in the University.

Physical education teachers may learn from this study and prepare themselves to implement the subject in college effectively. It may help them improve their learning instructions and approaches to pedagogy in teaching Physical Education.

As the primary beneficiaries of this study, the college PE students may activate their interest in learning the Physical Education subject. It provides them an avenue to develop skills with fun and suited to their interest as they perform various physical activities. Moreover, the students will have a meaningful learning experience that can apply in a real-life scenario.

Finally, future researchers may explore the result of this study and conduct a more comprehensive investigation of the Experiences of PE Students in the Implementation of the Physical Education Curriculum in the Senior High School Department. A comparison of the PE College Curriculum to the Senior High School PE curriculum would help improve the implementation of the PE Curriculum to avoid duplication of the Physical Activities that hinder the active participation of the students.

References

- Cariaga, J. (2014). The Physical Education Program of State Universities in Isabela: An Assessment. Philippine Normal University – North Luzon Campus, Isabela, Philippines. Research Journal of Physical Education Sciences. ISSN 2320– 9011 Vol. 2(10), 1-8, October (2014) Res. J. Physical Education Sci. International Science Congress Association. http://www.isca.in/PHY_EDU_SCI/Archive/v2/i10/1.ISCA-RJPES-2014-053.pdf
- Ganaden, A. (2019) Evaluating Quality Physical Education Program Of President Ramon Magsaysay State University, Zambales, Philippines. [http:// www.ijesrt.com](http://www.ijesrt.com)© International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology
- Haerens, L., Aelterman, N., Van den Berghe, L., De Meyer, J., Soenens, B., & Vansteenkiste, M. (2013). Observing physical education teachers' need-supportive interactions in classroom settings. *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 35,3-17.
- Lund, J.& Veal, M. L. (2018). Become A Good Assessor. This is an Excerpt from AssessmentDriven Instruction in Physical Education with Web Resource.<https://us.humankinetics.com/blogs/excerpt/become-a-good-assessor> 2018.
- Plakona, E., Parčina, I., Ludvig, A., & Tuzović, A. (2014). Self-confidence in sport. *Sport Science*, 7(1), 47-5.
- Rheingold, A. (2010). Engaging students in physical fitness: A case study of an adventure-based fitness program. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 32(3), 266-269. Retrieved from EBSCOhost
- Starc, G., Strel, J. Influence of the quality implementation of a physical education curriculum on the physical development and physical fitness of children. *BMC Public Health* 12, 61 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-12-61>
- Subramaniam, R., & Silverman, S. (2007). Middle school students' attitudes toward physical education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 23, 602–611
- Tagare, R., & Villaluz, G. (2021). Activity Preferences of Generation Z Students for Tertiary Physical Education: Implications for Curriculum Enhancement. *Multidisciplinary Journal for Education, Social and Technological Sciences*, 8(2), 92-106. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4995/muse.2021.15492>
- Tagare, Ruben Jr. (2021). Probing the delivery of tertiary physical education among the generation Z students in the transition years of Philippine K to 12. *Sport Education and Society*. 4. 355-359. 10.22271/kheljournal.2021.v8.i4f.2204.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Eliseo V. Villaganas Jr., PhD

Notre Dame of Marbel University – Philippines